

Euler Cordial Graphs

Jason D. Andoyo ^{a*}

^a University of Southeastern Philippines, Davao City, Republic of the Philippines.

Author’s contribution

The sole author designed, analysed, interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56557/ajpam/2025/v7i1237>

Open Peer Review History:

This journal follows the Advanced Open Peer Review policy. Identity of the Reviewers, Editor(s) and additional Reviewers, peer review comments, different versions of the manuscript, comments of the editors, etc are available here: <https://prh.globalpresshub.com/review-history/2219>

Original Research Article

Received: 28/08/2025
Published: 15/11/2025

Abstract

Let $\eta \geq 3$ be an odd integer. For a simple connected graph G of order n , a bijective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is called Euler cordial labeling modulo η if the induced function $f_\eta^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, defined by $f_\eta^*(uv) = 0$ whenever $\frac{[f(a)+f(b)]^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta}$ is even or $f(a) + f(b)$ and η are not relatively prime, and $f_\eta^*(uv) = 1$ whenever $\frac{[f(a)+f(b)]^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta}$ is odd, satisfies the condition $|e_{f_\eta^*}(0) - e_{f_\eta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ where $e_{f_\eta^*}(i)$ is the number of edges with label i ($i = 0, 1$). This study explores the Euler cordial labeling of path graphs, star graphs, complete bipartite graphs, bistar graphs, alternate cycle snake graphs, m -tuple star graphs, and book graphs. The path graphs P_η and $P_{2\eta}$, the alternate cycle snake graph $A_m(C_\eta)$ (if $\gcd((\eta + 3)/2, \eta) = 1$), and the book graph $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta, 2q}$ (if $\gcd((\eta + 5)/2, \eta) = 1$) were determined to admit Euler cordial labeling modulo η , where η is an odd integer with $\eta \geq 3$. Moreover, the star graphs S_p and S_{2p-1} , the complete bipartite graph $K_{q(p-1), q}$, the bistar graph $B_{p,p}$, and the m -tuple star graph $\mathcal{S}_{m,p}$ admit Euler cordial labeling modulo p , where p is an odd prime.

Keywords: Odd integer; graph; Euler cordial labeling.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: jasonandoyo8000@gmail.com;

1 Introduction

A simple graph $G = (V, E)$ consists of a *vertex set* $V = V(G)$ and an *edge set* $E = E(G)$, where E is the set of unordered pairs of distinct elements of V . The elements of V and E are called *vertices* and *edges*, respectively. If $|V| = n$ and $|E| = m$, then G is said to have *order* n and *size* m (Chartrand and Zhang, 2008). Graph labeling is an assignment of numbers or labels to the vertices and/or edges of a graph under certain conditions (Gallian, 2022). Among the various types of graph labeling, *cordial labeling*, introduced by Cahit (1987), is a binary vertex labeling in which each vertex is assigned a label 0 or 1, and each edge receives a label determined by the labels of its endpoints; moreover, the numbers of vertices and edges labeled 0 and 1 differ by at most one. This concept led to the formulation of different types of graph labeling, such as integer cordial labeling (Nicolas & Maya, 2016), divisor cordial labeling (Sharma & Parthiban, 2022), and Tribonacci cordial labeling (Gudin & Pedrano, 2025).

The Legendre cordial labeling (Andoyo & Rulete, 2025; Aravindan et al., 2020; Pedrano & Rulete, 2017), a recent variant of cordial labeling, is notable for being the first to explicitly use modulo an integer (in this case, an odd prime) in its labeling function, which is defined under the Legendre symbol. Inspired by this idea, the concept of *Euler cordial labeling* is introduced as a new variant of cordial labeling. In this notion, the labeling function operates under modulo an odd integer η , $\eta \geq 3$, and is defined based on the parity of the expression $\frac{a^{\phi(\eta)-1}}{\eta}$, which is an integer according to Euler's theorem if $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$.

The Euler cordial labeling is distinct from other variants of cordial labeling because it is the first to be constructed based on a modular arithmetic result, specifically Euler's Theorem. Unlike other variants that rely primarily on additive or parity conditions, this labeling incorporates modular exponentiation and coprimality through the expression $\frac{(f(a)+f(b))^{\phi(\eta)-1}}{\eta}$. Its definition establishes a clear connection between graph labeling and modular arithmetic, forming a hybrid of combinatorial and arithmetic structures. This uniqueness highlights its significance in bridging number theory and graph theory, offering a new perspective for developing modular-based cordial labeling.

2 Basic Concepts

Definition 2.1. A *path graph* P_n of order n is a graph with vertex set $V(P_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(P_n) = \{v_1v_2, v_2v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}v_n\}$.

Definition 2.2. A *cycle graph* C_n of order n , $n \geq 3$, is a graph with vertex set $V(C_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(C_n) = E(P_n) \cup \{v_1v_n\}$.

Definition 2.3. A *star graph* S_n of order n , $n \geq 2$, is a graph with vertex set $V(S_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}\} \cup \{x_0\}$ and edge set $E(S_n) = \{v_ix_0 : i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, where x_0 is called the *central vertex*.

Definition 2.4. A *complete bipartite graph* $K_{n,m}$ of order $n+m$ is a graph where the vertex set $V(K_{n,m})$ can be partitioned into two nonempty subsets V_1 and V_2 , with $|V_1| = n$ and $|V_2| = m$, such that every vertex in V_1 is adjacent to every vertex in V_2 , and no two vertices within the same subset are adjacent.

Definition 2.5. A *bistar graph* $B_{n,m}$ of order $n+m$ is created from two star graphs S_n and S_m such that the central vertex of S_n is adjacent to the central vertex of S_m .

Definition 2.6. An *alternate cycle snake graph* $A_n(C_m)$ of order nm is composed of cycle graphs $C_m^1, C_m^2, \dots, C_m^n$, with $V(C_m^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_m^j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, such that v_1^j is adjacent to v_m^{j+1} for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

Definition 2.7. An *m-tuple star graph* $S_{m,n}$ is created from m star graphs with order n such that the central vertices of these star graphs are adjacent to a new vertex z_0 .

Definition 2.8. A book graph $\mathfrak{B}_{n,m}$ of order $nm + 2$ is obtained from path graphs $P_n^1, P_n^2, \dots, P_n^m$, with $V(P_n^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_n^j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and path graph P_2 , with $V(P_2) = \{u_1, u_2\}$, such that $v_1^j u_1, v_n^j u_2 \in E(\mathfrak{B}_{m,n})$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Theorem 2.9. (Binomial Theorem) For any real number x and y , if n is a positive integer, then $(x + y)^n = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} x^i y^{n-i}$.

The following concepts are obtained from the elementary textbooks written by Burton (2011) and Rosen (2013).

Definition 2.10. The Euler phi function $\phi(\eta)$ is the number of positive integers not exceeding η that is relatively prime to η .

Theorem 2.11. If η is an integer with $\eta \geq 3$, then $\phi(\eta)$ is even.

Theorem 2.12. (Euler's Theorem) Let η be a positive integer and a be an integer with $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$. Then $a^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{\eta}$.

By Euler's Theorem, $\frac{a^{\phi(\eta)-1}}{\eta}$ is an integer whenever $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$. This motivates the creation of the following definition as a variant of cordial labeling based on the parity of $\frac{a^{\phi(\eta)-1}}{\eta}$.

Definition 2.13. Let η be odd with $\eta \geq 3$. For a simple connected graph G of order n , a bijective function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is called Euler cordial labeling modulo η if the induced function $f_\eta^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, defined by

$$f_\eta^*(ab) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \frac{[f(a) + f(b)]^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ or } \gcd(f(a) + f(b), \eta) \neq 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{[f(a) + f(b)]^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \end{cases}$$

satisfies the condition $|e_{f_\eta^*}(0) - e_{f_\eta^*}(1)| \leq 1$ where $e_{f_\eta^*}(i)$ is the number of edges with label i ($i = 0, 1$). A graph that admits this labeling is called Euler cordial graph modulo η .

3 Preliminary Results

Remark 3.1. If n is a positive integer, then $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{i} \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

Proof. By Theorem 2.9,

$$(1 + 1)^n = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i}$$

$$2^n = \binom{n}{0} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{i} + \binom{n}{n}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{i} = 2^n - 2.$$

Therefore, $\sum_{i=1}^{\eta-1} \binom{\eta}{i} \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. ■

Lemma 3.2. Let η be odd with $\eta \geq 3$. Suppose that $\zeta(a, \eta) = \frac{a^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta}$ for any integer a with $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$.

- i. If $\gcd(a, \eta) = \gcd(b, \eta)$, then $\zeta(a, \eta)$ and $\zeta(b, \eta)$ have opposite parities if and only if $b - a$ is odd. Equivalently, $\zeta(a, \eta)$ and $\zeta(b, \eta)$ have the same parity if and only if $b - a$ is even.
- ii. If $\zeta(a, \eta) \equiv k \pmod{2}$, then

$$\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta) \equiv \begin{cases} k \pmod{2} & \text{if } m \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ (1 - k) \pmod{2} & \text{if } m \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

where $k \in \{0, 1\}$.

- iii. Suppose that $\varphi(\eta) = \{\xi : \gcd(\xi, \eta) = 1, 0 < \xi < \eta\}$. For $a \in \varphi(\eta)$ and $m \geq 0$, define

$$A_m = \{a + m\eta : \zeta(a + m\eta, \eta) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}\},$$

$$B_m = \{a + m\eta : \zeta(a + m\eta, \eta) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}\}.$$

Then $|A_m| = |B_m| = \frac{\phi(\eta)}{2}$ for all $m \geq 0$.

- iv. $\zeta(\eta + 1 + m\eta, \eta)$ and $\zeta(\eta + 2 + m\eta, \eta)$ have opposite parities for all $m \geq 0$.

Proof. Because η is odd, $\eta \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. In addition, we need the following facts: For every integer a , $a^m \equiv a \pmod{2}$ where m is a positive integer; The integers a and b have opposite parities if and only if $b - a \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$; If $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$, then $\gcd(a + m\eta, \eta) = 1$ for all m .

(i): (\Rightarrow) Observe the following,

$$\zeta(b, \eta) - \zeta(a, \eta) = \frac{b^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta} - \frac{a^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta} = \frac{b^{\phi(\eta)} - a^{\phi(\eta)}}{\eta}.$$

Since $\zeta(a, \eta)$ and $\zeta(b, \eta)$ have opposite parities, we have

$$\frac{b^{\phi(\eta)} - a^{\phi(\eta)}}{\eta} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$b^{\phi(\eta)} - a^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv \eta \pmod{2}$$

$$b - a \equiv 1 \pmod{2}.$$

Hence, $b - a$ is odd.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose $b - a$ is odd, that is, $b - a \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Thus, by Theorem 2.9,

$$(b - a)^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\phi(\eta)} \binom{\phi(\eta)}{i} b^i (-a)^{\phi(\eta)-i} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$(-a)^{\phi(\eta)} + \sum_{i=1}^{\phi(\eta)-1} \binom{\phi(\eta)}{i} b^i (-a)^{\phi(\eta)-i} + b^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}.$$

Since $\phi(\eta)$ is even by Theorem 2.11, $(-a)^{\phi(\eta)} = a^{\phi(\eta)}$. Using Remark 3.1, we have

$$a^{\phi(\eta)} - \sum_{i=1}^{\phi(\eta)-1} \binom{\phi(\eta)}{i} ba + b^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$a^{\phi(\eta)} + b^{\phi(\eta)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$-2a^{\phi(\eta)} + a^{\phi(\eta)} + 1 + b^{\phi(\eta)} - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$(b^{\phi(\eta)} - 1) - (a^{\phi(\eta)} - 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

Since $\eta\zeta(a, \eta) = a^{\phi(\eta)} - 1$ and $\eta\zeta(b, \eta) = b^{\phi(\eta)} - 1$,

$$\eta\zeta(b, \eta) - \eta\zeta(a, \eta) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$\zeta(b, \eta) - \zeta(a, \eta) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}.$$

Consequently, $\zeta(a, \eta)$ and $\zeta(b, \eta)$ have opposite parities.

(ii): Observe that $a + m\eta - a = m\eta$. If $m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then $m\eta$ is even and by (i), $\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta) \equiv k \pmod{2}$. Similarly, if $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then $m\eta$ is odd and so, $\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta) \equiv (1 - k) \pmod{2}$ according to (i).

(iii): Consider the number $\eta - a$. Since $0 < a < \eta$, we have $0 < \eta - a < \eta$. If $d = \gcd(\eta - a, \eta)$, then d divides the difference $\eta - (\eta - a) = a$. Given that $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$, it follows that $d = 1$. Thus, $\eta - a \in \varphi(\eta)$. Also, it is clear that $\eta - a \neq a$. Next, by (i), $\zeta(\eta - a + m\eta, \eta)$ and $\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta)$ have opposite parities since $\eta - a + m\eta - (a + m\eta) = \eta - 2a$ is odd. Without loss of generality, suppose that $a + m\eta \in A_m$ and $\eta - a + m\eta \in B_m$. Let $F: A_m \rightarrow B_m$ be a function defined by

$$F(a + m\eta) = \eta - a + m\eta.$$

This is a well-defined function since $\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta)$ is odd if and only if $\zeta(\eta - a + m\eta, \eta)$ is even. This function can be written in the form $F(x) = x + c$ where $x = a + m\eta$ and $c = \eta - 2a$. Obviously, F is a bijective function. Thus, $|A_m| = |B_m|$. Because A_m and B_m form a partition of the set $\{\zeta(a + m\eta, \eta): a \in \varphi(\eta)\}$ which has cardinality $\phi(\eta)$, we have $|A_m| = |B_m| = \frac{\phi(\eta)}{2}$ for all $m \geq 0$.

(iv): Immediately follows (i).

4 Main Results

In the following results, we assume that η is an odd integer with $\eta \geq 3$ and let p be an odd prime. Note that $\phi(p) = p - 1$. In addition, suppose that $\zeta(a, \eta) = \frac{a^{\phi(\eta)} - 1}{\eta}$ for any integer a relatively prime to η . Lastly, we always use the fact that if $\gcd(a, \eta) = 1$, then $\gcd(a + m\eta, \eta) = 1$ for all integer m .

Theorem 4.1. The path graphs P_η and $P_{2\eta}$ are Euler cordial graphs modulo η .

Proof. Let $V(P_\eta) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_\eta\}$. Suppose $f: V(P_\eta) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, \eta\}$ is a function defined by

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{i+1}{2} & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta \\ \eta - \frac{i-2}{2} & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1. \end{cases}$$

Thus, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of P_η ,

$$f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1}) = \begin{cases} \eta + 1 & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta - 2 \\ \eta + 2 & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1. \end{cases}$$

By Lemma 3.2 (iv), $\zeta(\eta + 1, \eta)$ and $\zeta(\eta + 2, \eta)$ have opposite parities. Therefore, $e_{f_\eta^*}(0) = e_{f_\eta^*}(1) = \frac{\eta-1}{2}$ and it follows that $|e_{f_\eta^*}(0) - e_{f_\eta^*}(1)| = 0$. Consequently, P_η is an Euler cordial graph modulo η .

For $P_{2\eta}$, assume that $V(P_{2\eta}) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2\eta}\}$ and define the function $f: V(P_{2\eta}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2\eta\}$ by

$$f(v_{i+\eta(j-1)}) = \begin{cases} \frac{i+1}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta \\ \eta - \frac{i-2}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1 \end{cases}$$

for $j = 1, 2$. Clearly, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of $P_{2\eta}$,

$$f(v_{i+\eta(j-1)}) + f(v_{i+1+\eta(j-1)}) = \begin{cases} \eta + 1 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta - 2 \\ \eta + 2 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1 \end{cases}$$

for $j = 1, 2$ and $f(v_\eta) + f(v_{\eta+1}) = \frac{\eta+1}{2} + 1 + 2\eta$. Since $\zeta(\eta + 1 + 2\eta(j-1))$ and $\zeta(\eta + 2 + 2\eta(j-1))$ have opposite parities according to Lemma 3.2 (iv), for $j = 1, 2$, we have

$$e_{f_\eta^*}(0) = \begin{cases} \eta & \text{if } f_\eta^*(v_\eta v_{\eta+1}) = 0 \\ \eta - 1 & \text{if } f_\eta^*(v_\eta v_{\eta+1}) = 1, \end{cases}$$

$$e_{f_\eta^*}(1) = \begin{cases} \eta - 1 & \text{if } f_\eta^*(v_\eta v_{\eta+1}) = 0 \\ \eta & \text{if } f_\eta^*(v_\eta v_{\eta+1}) = 1. \end{cases}$$

Therefore, $|e_{f_\eta^*}(0) - e_{f_\eta^*}(1)| = 1$. Thus, $P_{2\eta}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo η . ■

Fig. 1. Euler cordial labeling modulo 7 of P_7

Fig. 2. Euler cordial labeling modulo 5 of P_{10}

Theorem 4.2. The star graph S_{2p-1} are Euler cordial graphs modulo p .

Proof. Suppose that $V(S_{2p-1}) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2p-1}\}$ and let v_p be the central vertex. Let $f: V(S_{2p-1}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2p-1\}$ be a function defined by $f(v_i) = i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2p-1$. Hence, f is a bijective function. For the edges of S_{2p-1} , $f(v_i) + f(v_p) = i + p$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2p-1, i \neq p$. Suppose that

$$\beta = \{f(v_i) + f(v_p) : i = 1, 2, \dots, p-1\},$$

$$\gamma = \{f(v_i) + f(v_p) : i = p+1, p+2, \dots, 2p-1\}.$$

As a result,

$$\beta = \{1+p, 2+p, \dots, p-1+p\},$$

$$\gamma = \{1+2p, 2+2p, \dots, p-1+2p\}.$$

Therefore, using Lemma 3.2 (iii), $e_{f_p^*}(0) = e_{f_p^*}(1) = 2 \binom{p-1}{2} = p-1$. Thus, $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$. Consequently, S_{2p-1} is an Euler cordial graph modulo p . ■

Fig. 3. Euler cordial labeling modulo 5 of S_9

Theorem 4.3. The complete bipartite graph $K_{q(p-1),q}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p for $q \geq 1$.

Proof. Let V_1 and V_2 be partite sets of $K_{q(p-1),q}$ with $V_1 = \mathbb{V}^1 \cup \mathbb{V}^2 \cup \dots \cup \mathbb{V}^q$, where $\mathbb{V}^j = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_{p-1}^j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, q$, and $V_2 = \{v_p^1, v_p^2, \dots, v_p^q\}$. Assume that $f: V(K_{q(p-1),q}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, qp\}$ is a function defined by $f(v_i^j) = i + p(j-1)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, q$. Clearly, f is a bijective function. Note that all vertices in \mathbb{V}^j are adjacent to v_p^k for $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, q$. Hence,

$$f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^k) = i + p(j-1) + p + p(k-1) = i + p(j+k-1)$$

for $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, q$. In view of this labeling, define

$$\alpha_{j,k} = \{f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^k) : i = 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$$

and so

$$\alpha_{j,k} = \{1 + p(j+k-1), 2 + p(j+k-1), \dots, p-1 + p(j+k-1)\}$$

for $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, q$. By Lemma 3.2 (iii), $e_{f_p^*}(0) = e_{f_p^*}(1) = q \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)$. Hence, $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$ and it follows that $K_{q(p-1),q}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p . ■

Fig. 4. Euler cordial labeling modulo 5 of $K_{8,2}$

Theorem 4.4. The bistar graph $B_{p,p}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Suppose that S_p^1 and S_p^2 are star graphs of $B_{p,p}$ with $V(S_p^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_p^j\}$ where v_p^j is the central vertex, for $j = 1, 2$. Define the function $f: V(B_{p,p})$ by $f(v_i^j) = i + p(j - 1)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ and $j = 1, 2$. Hence, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of $B_{p,p}$,

$$f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^j) = i + p(2j - 1) \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1,$$

for $j = 1, 2$, and $f(v_p^1) + f(v_p^2) = 3p$. Suppose that

$$\alpha_j = \{f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^j) : i = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}$$

for $j = 1, 2$. Thus,

$$\alpha_j = \{1 + p(2j - 1), 2 + p(2j - 1), \dots, p - 1 + p(2j - 1)\}$$

for $j = 1, 2$. By Lemma 3.2 (iii), together with the fact that $f_p^*(v_p^1 v_p^2) = 0$ (since $\gcd(3p, p) \neq 1$), we obtain $e_{f_p^*}(0) = 2 \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right) + 1 = p$ and $e_{f_p^*}(1) = 2 \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right) = p - 1$. Hence, $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 1$ and so $B_{p,p}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p . ■

Fig. 5. Euler cordial labeling modulo 7 of $B_{7,7}$

Theorem 4.5. The alternate cycle snake graph $A_m(C_\eta)$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo η if $\gcd\left(\frac{\eta+3}{2}, \eta\right) = 1$, for $m \geq 2$.

Proof. Suppose that $C_\eta^1, C_\eta^2, \dots, C_\eta^m$ are cycles of $A_m(C_\eta)$ with $V(C_\eta^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_\eta^j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Assume that $f: V(A_m(C_\eta)) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, m\eta\}$ is a function defined by

$$f(v_i^j) = \begin{cases} \frac{i+1}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta \\ \eta - \frac{i-2}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta-1 \end{cases}$$

For $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Clearly, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of $A_m(C_\eta)$,

$$f(v_i^j) + f(v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} \eta + 1 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta-2 \\ \eta + 2 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta-1, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_1^j) + f(v_\eta^j) = \frac{\eta+3}{2} + 2\eta j - 2\eta,$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and

$$f(v_1^j) + f(v_\eta^{j+1}) = \frac{\eta+3}{2} + 2\eta j - \eta$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$.

According to Lemma (ii), $\zeta\left(\frac{\eta+3}{2} + 2\eta j - 2\eta, \eta\right)$ and $\zeta\left(\frac{\eta+3}{2} + 2\eta j - \eta, \eta\right)$ have opposite parities, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$. Also, by Lemma (iv), $\zeta(\eta + 1 + 2\eta(j-1), \eta)$ and $\zeta(\eta + 2 + 2\eta(j-1), \eta)$ have opposite parities, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Therefore,

$$e_{f_{\eta}^*}(0) = \begin{cases} m\left(\frac{\eta-1}{2}\right) + m & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(v_1^m v_{\eta}^m) = 0 \\ m\left(\frac{\eta-1}{2}\right) + m - 1 & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(v_1^m v_{\eta}^m) = 1, \end{cases}$$

$$e_{f_{\eta}^*}(1) = \begin{cases} m\left(\frac{\eta-1}{2}\right) + m - 1 & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(v_1^m v_{\eta}^m) = 0 \\ m\left(\frac{\eta-1}{2}\right) + m & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(v_1^m v_{\eta}^m) = 1. \end{cases}$$

It follows that $|e_{f_{\eta}^*}(0) - e_{f_{\eta}^*}(1)| = 1$. Consequently, $A_m(C_{\eta})$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo η .

Fig. 6. Euler cordial labeling modulo 5 of $A_3(C_5)$

Theorem 4.6. The m -tuple star graph $\mathcal{S}_{m,p}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p for $m \geq 2$.

Proof. Let $S_p^1, S_p^2, \dots, S_p^m$ be star graphs of $\mathcal{S}_{m,p}$ with $V(S_p^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_p^j\}$ where v_p^j is the central vertex, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Suppose that x_0 is a vertex of $\mathcal{S}_{m,p}$ such that $v_p^j x_0 \in E(\mathcal{S}_{m,p})$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Let $f: V(\mathcal{S}_{m,p}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, mp + 1\}$ be a function defined by

$$f(v_i^j) = i + p(j - 1) \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, p \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m,$$

$$f(x_0) = mp + 1.$$

Evidently, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of S_p^j ,

$$f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^j) = i + p(2j - 1) \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1,$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Define the set

$$\alpha_j = \{f(v_i^j) + f(v_p^j) : i = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}$$

and so

$$\alpha_j = \{1 + p(2j - 1), 2 + p(2j - 1), \dots, p - 1 + p(2j - 1)\}$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. By Lemma 3.2 (iii), for each $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ edges of S_p^j with label 0 and $\frac{p-1}{2}$ edges with label 1, under f_p^* .

For the remaining edges,

$$f(v_p^j) + f(x_0) = 1 + p(j + m)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. By Lemma 3.2 (ii), $\zeta(1 + p(k + m), p)$ and $\zeta(1 + p(k + 1 + m), p)$ have opposite parities, for $k = 1, 3, \dots, m - \varepsilon$, where

$$\varepsilon = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Combining all the arguments above, if $m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$,

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = e_{f_p^*}(1) = m \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + \frac{m}{2}.$$

Also, if $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$,

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = \begin{cases} m \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + \frac{m-1}{2} + 1 & \text{if } f_p^*(v_p^m x_0) = 0 \\ m \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + \frac{m-1}{2} & \text{if } f_p^*(v_p^m x_0) = 1, \end{cases}$$

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = \begin{cases} m \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + \frac{m-1}{2} & \text{if } f_p^*(v_p^m x_0) = 0 \\ m \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + \frac{m-1}{2} + 1 & \text{if } f_p^*(v_p^m x_0) = 1. \end{cases}$$

In either case, $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$. Therefore, $\mathcal{S}_{m,p}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo p . ■

Fig. 7. Euler cordial labeling modulo 5 of $\mathcal{S}_{3,5}$

Theorem 4.7. The book graph $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo η if $\gcd\left(\frac{\eta+5}{2}, \eta\right) = 1$, for $q \geq 1$.

Proof. Let $P_{\eta}^1, P_{\eta}^2, \dots, P_{\eta}^{2q}$ be path graphs of $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}$ with $V(P_{\eta}^j) = \{v_1^j, v_2^j, \dots, v_{\eta}^j\}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, 2q$. Suppose that P_2 is a path graph of $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}$ with $V(P_2) = \{u_1, u_2\}$. Define the function $f: V(\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2q\eta + 2\}$ by

$$f(v_i^j) = \begin{cases} \frac{i+1}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta \\ \eta - \frac{i-2}{2} + \eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1 \end{cases} \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, 2q,$$

$$f(u_i) = 2q\eta + i \text{ for } i = 1, 2.$$

Obviously, f is a bijective function.

For the edges of $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}$,

$$f(v_i^j) + f(v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} \eta + 1 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 1, 3, \dots, \eta - 2 \\ \eta + 2 + 2\eta(j-1) & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, \eta - 1, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_1^j) + f(u_1) = 2 + \eta[2q + j - 1],$$

$$f(v_{\eta}^j) + f(u_2) = \frac{\eta + 5}{2} + \eta[2q + j - 1],$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, 2q$, and $f(u_1) + f(u_2) = 4q\eta + 3$.

Using Lemma 3.2 (ii), $\zeta(2 + \eta[2q + k - 1], \eta)$ and $\zeta(2 + \eta[2q + k], \eta)$ have opposite parities, for $k = 1, 3, \dots, 2q - 1$. Similarly, for each $k = 1, 3, \dots, 2q - 1$, $\zeta\left(\frac{\eta+5}{2} + \eta[2q + k - 1], \eta\right)$ and $\zeta\left(\frac{\eta+5}{2} + \eta[2q + k], \eta\right)$ have opposite parities by Lemma 3.2 (ii). Also, $\zeta(\eta + 1 + 2\eta(j - 1), \eta)$ and $\zeta(\eta + 2 + 2\eta(j - 1), \eta)$ have opposite parities, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, 2q$, in accordance with Lemma 3.2 (iv). Thus,

$$e_{f_{\eta}^*}(0) = \begin{cases} 2q + q(\eta - 1) + 1 & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(u_1 u_2) = 0 \\ 2q + q(\eta - 1) & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(u_1 u_2) = 1, \end{cases}$$

$$e_{f_{\eta}^*}(1) = \begin{cases} 2q + q(\eta - 1) & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(u_1 u_2) = 0 \\ 2q + q(\eta - 1) + 1 & \text{if } f_{\eta}^*(u_1 u_2) = 1. \end{cases}$$

Hence, $|e_{f_{\eta}^*}(0) - e_{f_{\eta}^*}(1)| = 1$. Therefore, $\mathfrak{B}_{\eta,2q}$ is an Euler cordial graph modulo η .

modular congruence relations in distinct ways, opening new avenues for exploring the intersection of number theory and graph labeling.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that no generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges the Department of Science and Technology – Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI), Philippines, for the financial support provided through the STRAND scholarship program, which made this publication possible.

Competing Interests

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Andoyo, J.D., & Rulete, R.F. (2025). On Legendre cordial labeling of some graphs. *European Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 6(5), 1-7. <https://www.ej-math.org/index.php/ejmath/article/view/409>
- Aravindan, S. J., Sasikala, D., & Divya, A. (2020). Visualization of cordial graph in human excretion track. *Italian Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 44, 460-469. https://ijpam.uniud.it/online_issue/202044/40%20Divya-Aravindan-Sasikala.pdf
- Burton, D.M. (2011). *Elementary Number Theory*. McGraw Hill. <https://www.mheducation.com/highered/product/elementary-number-theory-burton.html?viewOption=student>
- Cahit, I. (1987). Cordial graphs: a weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs. *Ars Combinatoria*, 23, 201-207. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233792958_Cordial_Graphs_A_Weaker_Version_of_Graceful_and_Harmonious_Graphs
- Chartrand, G., & Zhang, P. (2008). *Chromatic Graph Theory*. Taylor and Francis Group. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.1201/9781584888017/chromatic-graph-theory-gary-chartrand-ping-zhang>
- Gallian, J.A. (2022). A Dynamic Survey of Graph Labeling (25th ed). *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*. <https://www.combinatorics.org/files/Surveys/ds6/ds6v25-2022.pdf>
- Gudin, M.V., & Pedrano, A. (2025). Tribonacci Cordial Labeling of Some Snake Graphs. *Annals of Communication in Mathematics*. 8(3), 393-405. <https://www.technoskypub.com/journals/acm-2025-080306/>
- Nicholas, T., & Maya, P. (2016). Some results on integer cordial graph. *Journal of Progressive research in Mathematics (JPRM)*, 8(1), 1183-1194. <https://scitecresearch.com/journals/index.php/jprm/article/view/786>

Pedrano, A. C., & Rulete, R. F. On the total product cordial labeling on the cartesian product of $P_m \times C_n$, $C_m \times C_n$ and the generalized Petersen graph $P(m, n)$. *Malaya J. Mat.* 5(3) (2017) 531–539
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317913334>

Rosen K.H. (2013). *Elementary Number Theory and its applications* (6th ed.). Pearson.
<https://www.pearson.com/en-gb/subject-catalog/p/elementary-number-theory-pearson-new-international-edition/P200000005328/9781292055145>

Sharma, V., & Parthiban, A. (2022). On Divisor Cordial Labeling of Certain Classes of Planar Graphs. *Journal of Algebraic Statistics*, 13(2), 1421-1425.
<https://publishoa.com/index.php/journal/article/view/304>

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of the publisher and/or the editor(s). This publisher and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

© Copyright (2025): Author(s). The licensee is the journal publisher. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here (Please copy paste the total link in your browser address bar)

<https://prh.globalpresshub.com/review-history/2219>